

A Review of Challenges as Educational Innovations in Higher Education

C. P. Shivachandra, Research Scholar, Kannada Adhyayana Peetha, Hampi
and

Chaitra Pandurang Naik, Research Scholar, Dept. of English, Karnatak
University Dharwad

E.Mail:cpshivachandra@gmail.com

Received: 16/11/2022

Accepted: 01/12/2022

Published: 15/01/2023

Abstract

The growth of society and the direction in which it must go are extensively determined, partly by education. Since it has been a critical factor in the accomplishment of several social achievements. Since growth and progress are the rules of the day, education has come to the fore and gained essential importance. The goal of the current article is to provide some insight into the current situation of higher education, the gross enrollment ratio, and the employability of the schools' output. Higher education institutions' main focus is to provide high-quality education and to create employability in the education sector. We manage to thrive in a world where education is the cornerstone for climbing the social, political, economic, etc. social ladder. The report also emphasizes the innovativeness being created, pursued, and used due to the shifting global educational landscape.

Keywords: Higher education, Higher Learning Institutions, Demographic Dividend, Social Capital, Curriculum

Chaitra Pandurang Naik, E.Mail:cpshivachandra@gmail.com

1. Introduction

In recent years, India's economy has been expanding at an ever-increasing pace. It has emerged as a significant force in the modern information economy worldwide. Expertise-based endeavors have been a major factor in the expansion. Such endeavors need the availability of highly educated and skilled labor; it will provide the country's extensive system of higher learning. Higher education in India has mainly been credited as a critical factor in the country's rise to prominence in the global knowledge economy. There is a concern, however, that the Indian university system is in danger. The Prime Minister's NKC describes it as a "silent crisis," while the Minister of Human Resources refers to higher education as "a sick kid." Industries consistently highlight massive talent shortages, expressing concern that economic momentum will be lost if the issues do not vanish. The problems plaguing Indian higher education seem to be never-ending. Some of the problems include a cumbersome affiliation system, an inflexible academic organization, unequal capability across topics, an erosion of educational institutions' autonomy, a low amount of public support, and a dysfunctional regulatory environment. Finally, there is a consensus that is plagued by several structural flaws and is motivated by populism. Due to a lack of reliable data, there is no informed public discussion. [1]

More than 35 years ago, Nobel laureate Amartya Sen pointed out that the "grave failures in policy-making: in the education sector require the analysis of the characteristics of the social and economic forces operating in India, & response of public policy to these forces' ". As he put it, "owing to the government's predisposition to design educational policies based on popular pressure, sometimes erroneous policies are adopted." Relative shortcomings are thought to exist in policymaking today, which is a sad reality. Instead of realism, policymakers are motivated by populism, dogma, and special interests. Aims are chosen randomly, and success is frequently elusive and, worse, only half-heartedly pursued.[2]

Some academics have regarded educational innovations as tough, technically and emotionally demanding, and complicated, although enormous resources have been invested in their creation and implementation. Therefore, it is essential to consider whether or not new education methods may influence higher education.

For educational innovations to have a more significant impact, they need to be widely adopted, and "networks of educational innovation" may facilitate this process by allowing educators at the university level to collaborate and learn from one another. These connections

don't just happen, so you'll need to build them intentionally. Because of the importance of fostering professional communities among higher education instructors, many educational reform projects adopt a variety of tactics to encourage such networks, such as networking events, training, and teaching conferences.[3]

Researchers have hypothesized that educational networks may improve the quality of higher education instruction, but there is little data to back up these claims. It is suggested by some academics that the educational networks fostered and maintained by reform attempts may function in a restricted, focused, and outcome-oriented manner, stifling the spread of innovations. Others, however, have discovered that the traits of educational innovators, such as the strategic use of networks, are beneficial for introducing new ideas into higher education. Though higher education's ability to facilitate the spread of new ideas and technologies via its networked educational (innovation) initiatives has been the subject of some research, very few studies have analyzed these networks in detail. More study is required to understand the effects of faculty characteristics on network architecture in higher education.[4]

2. **Higher Education's Evolution**

The time-honored method of providing university education in India has been around for a long time, As a result, it has inherited a wealth of experience and wisdom that has fostered the development of its culture and its people from the dawn of Indian civilization. During the Gupta era, patronage of educational institutions like Nalanda, Takshila, Ujjain, Vikramshila, and Vallabhi was fostered. As was previously noted, each school has its area of academic expertise. In the seventh and eighth centuries A.D., this kind of University flourished. People rushed to Sarnath University to study Buddhism and to Ajanta to become experts in the field of art, architecture, and painting after the spread of Buddhism. Donations and land gifts are the primary sources of revenue for these establishments. Kings and other wealthy members of society at the time made such donations. Evidence from ancient times suggests that this system has been in place in India since at least 1000 B.C. Compared to the European tradition, the system's knowledge creation, assumptions on which knowledge was built, and fundamental conceptions of organizational learning were radically different.[5]

2.1 System of Higher Education During The British Raj

In 1857, the British Government established European-style universities in Bombay, Calcutta, and Madras, bringing the European system of higher education to India for the first time. The British did a lot to advance English in a higher education system, starting with the inception of the British Raj in 1858. One of the critical contributions of the government was the establishment of English-language schools and the encouragement of the use of English in academic settings.

2.2 The States and Federal Government Contribution to Develop Present Education System in India :

Increasing access to higher education has been a driving force in India's rapid economic development, as the country's emphasis is on cultivating its own talent pool. Education is a hot topic in the present time, and states and federal governments play a significant role in expanding access to and quality of higher education by funding and supporting the development of universities and colleges. The following tables provide a snapshot and history of India's tertiary education system.

Table 1: Number of Institutions in 2020–2021

No. of Institutions	Year (2020-2021)
AICTE Technical Institutions	12069
Universities	513
Distance teaching Institutions and Universities	260
Colleges	34013

Table 2: enrollment for the academic year 2020–21

Open distance learning enrollment (In Lakhs)	34.25
Admission to Universities with AICTE approval (In Lakhs)	21.5
Enrollment in colleges and institutions (In Lakhs)	179.6
Enrollment in post-secondary or post-graduate studies (In Lakhs)	15.56

Following India's independence, the country's higher education system has expanded rapidly, with several new Universities and colleges opening their doors to students. From only 20 in 1950, there are now 677 Universities in the world in 2014. There are 51 Institutions of National Importance, 45 Central Universities, 318 State Universities, 185 Private Universities, 129 Deemed to be Universities, and 4 IISERs under MHRD. College enrollment has also increased dramatically, from 500 in 1950 to 37,204 as of March 31st 2013. Historically, India's population was significantly lower, and more people had the opportunity to go to college. However, a significant increase in the population has made it difficult to gain entry to universities and other institutions of higher education in India. It has been discovered that increased high cut-off percentages for admission as 80%, 85%, and even 90% have implemented by some of the most prestigious Universities and organizations in India. The ultimate responsibility lies with the nation's educators. They should become the true torchbearers in the eyes of the student body by teaching and demonstrating integrity and a commitment to carrying out their obligations. That, all by itself, may elevate the University or college campus beyond preconceived notions. The trend of instructors engaging in private tutoring has spread like a disease. It must be reduced and managed, if necessary, by legal means.[6]

3. Challenges in Higher Education

The structure of American higher education is intricate and vast. Challenges have been mounting for Higher Education institutions worldwide for the past decade. There has been a lot of attention paid to pinpointing such difficulties in recent years. Twenty challenges identified in the literature are briefly discussed here:

3.1 Alignment

It has suggested that universities and colleges should adapt to the public's evolving demands. From a pedagogical standpoint, the SemTech initiative highlighted curriculum design as one of the most pressing issues in higher education. It has been recommended that colleges be quicker to implement new study programs and courses. Higher education institutions in the twenty-first century need to adapt to a more competitive international market by providing students with a range of degree and certificate options that cater to their interests and goals. Courses, programs, and institutional structures in higher education need to be updated to accommodate students who are both more academically accomplished and more

versed in the market. Students' expectations of the courses they take and the quality of those courses have grown in tandem with their rising financial investment, and universities should reflect these changes. However, mobility can be only achieved if degrees and credits earned are recognized universally. It requires accommodating variety and originality without stifling either. Therefore, higher education institutions must revise or reorient their curricula to better equip today's students for success in a global economy. Every school has to rethink its curriculum to improve education standards. Developing new courses is one of the most pressing problems in higher education. Through curriculum alignment, no student will fall behind, and everyone will have an equal chance to succeed in this age of globalization.[7]

3.2 Students' Employment

Globally, employability is still a significant focus for universities. Educating oneself is becoming more critical for people to do well in the modern labor market. A rising number of students and recent graduates see earning a degree as essential to launching a successful career, making employability a pressing issue. And selling, education and catering to commercial demands: the new educational agenda. Gaining more education and experience may significantly improve one's prospects and income. Definitions of employability vary but generally agree on the following: a person's employability is increased when they possess the set of skills, knowledge, and personal traits that increase their odds of securing and succeeding in a specific career. Learning outcomes in a program that include opportunities for parallel personal growth, such as job experience and extracurricular activities, are increasingly important in defining employability.

Universities and colleges must do more to help their students find jobs after graduation. Higher education institutions may react by including companies in the course validation process, which will guarantee that academic standards satisfy employer criteria and will have a positive impact on both the degree subject selection process and the relevance of graduates to the labour market. Companies must provide internships and job experience for students, and colleges and institutions must be more accommodating to their wants and requirements. In the 21st century, curricula should give substantial consideration to students' employability by including vital skills in the curriculum. For the sake of their students and their reputations, HEIs would be well to take the required measures to solve this problem promptly.[8]

3.3 Expanded Participation

Higher education has seen an uptick in demand as the application of newly acquired skills in the workplace has become more critical. However, access to higher education is hampered by socioeconomic status, rising tuition costs, the replacement of loans for grants, the reduction of government support for student facilities, and so on. Insufficient numbers of students from low-income families and underrepresented groups enroll in college. According to the Federal Government Advisory Board on Student Financial Assistance: Nearly 4,00,000 capable students every year do not pursue higher education because of lack of money. Current demand exists in many nations to increase the number of students enrolled in higher education. The goal of the United Kingdom is for at least half of the young population to enrol in higher education; as stated, U.K. policymakers have prioritized expanding access to higher education by increasing financing for higher education institutions since 1997. One of the primary missions of the 1 Higher Education Spending Council for England is to increase access to and participation in higher education (HEFCE). Access to higher education is highlighted as an issue that HE institutions must address.[9]

3.4 Excellence in Education and Instruction

It is especially fitting for institutions of higher education to place a premium on maintaining quality. The only way for a higher education institution to gain international credibility is to invest in the quality of its instruction and research. If higher education institutions cannot provide assurances of good quality, they will lose prospective students. Enabling access to learning and teaching materials across institutions is one way higher education institutions may improve the quality of education. As a result, students and educators have access to a wider breadth of knowledge in their respective fields of study. When it comes to the education of its students, higher education facilities have a responsibility to guarantee the highest standards of excellence are always met. The universities all share a commitment to maintaining a high standard of education. To that end, the United States government has established FIPSE. However, with tuition making up such a significant part of a university's budget, institutions have been compelled to raise the bar on their pedagogical offerings. Since 1997, the British government has allocated more resources toward enhancing the quality of instruction in higher education. Quality of education is identified as a significant problem in higher education by several writers. HEFCE is an organization whose mission is to "guarantee that all students in higher education in the UK

have a high-quality learning experience that completely satisfies their requirements and the demands of society." [10]

3.5 Research Quality

Research capability has to be bolstered at THE institutions if they want to compete with the finest in the world. To raise this challenge, academic institutions will need to create interdisciplinary centers that bring together specialists from many fields and foster connections between academic and business groups to solidify their research capabilities. The British government is committed to preserving research quality. Thus, it has allocated more resources to the cause. In addition, this will need a heightened emphasis on cutting-edge research and a broader acknowledgment of the potential advantages of concentrating research efforts in the central region. 1 HEFCE's mission in the United Kingdom is to foster a thriving and globally competitive research industry that significantly contributes to the country's economic growth, social welfare, and knowledge base. Several authors also highlighted research quality assurance as a crucial responsibility for universities in the 21st century. [11]

3.6 Accreditation

Accreditation is the most critical aspect of quality assurance in higher education and one of the significant mechanisms of delivering responsibility for THE Institutions and programmes. The capacity of universities to draw in students, research funding agencies, and corporate sponsors is hampered. In the United States, students may only receive federal financial help from the government if the school or any type programs students are enrolled for the course has been granted accreditation by an official body. Because of this, it has gained more significance in higher education. Accreditations are listed as a critical obstacle in higher education. The results of students' education are given primary consideration in all accreditation evaluations. Accreditation is a highly reliable guarantee of high standards in education. Institutions in higher education may help professional organizations effectively accredit their institutions or programs by making relevant data available. The information needed for effective accreditation is often spread among many departments within an institution.[12]

3.7 Engage in international research and talent competition

Top students, academics, and researchers are in high demand worldwide. Education and research programs must be of high quality for institutions to remain relevant. To remain competitive with other higher education institutions and to get worldwide recognition, higher education centers must maintain a better level of research. By maximizing their research potential, higher education institutions may forge high-quality partnerships with their

counterparts in other countries higher education systems. As a result, universities and colleges are realizing that they need to work together with their peers in the field, as well as with businesses, communities, and governments throughout the world, To take advantage of the possibilities presented by globalization fully. [13]

3.8 Academic Success

Today's HE Institutions have many students from different regions and countries. HE Institutions are increasingly recognizing that to gain public support and participation and to make higher standards of the institutions; they need to become more focused on student retention. The SemTech project identified student retention as one of the HE challenges. HE Institutions need to focus on student retention with more effective student support. HE Institutions are monitoring students' overall progress, and based on their information, they can take necessary steps for the students from the very beginning. They also need to take into account from the very beginning why students take off from a program or any specific modules. They need to focus on this issue to improve retention. 2 JISC is doing this to help improve student retention and motivation in UK Higher Education. [14]

3.9 Utilizing new Technology

The communications, economics, and even the day-to-day organization of the modern world are all powered by technological advancements. The proliferation of new IT resources for higher learning is a direct result of the industry's fast evolution. As a result of technological advancements, nowadays everyone may take advantage of educational possibilities whenever and wherever they like. In addition, the reaction of tertiary education institutions to this cutting-edge technology has been surprisingly swift. Universities' capacity to adapt to new or shifting markets might be hampered by their reluctance to engage in technology-based learning. Connections to material, context, and community may result in a more meaningful learning experience for students when teachers use tools like the internet as well as its related technology. NCATE is increasing the emphasis on technology in its performance-based standards for the year 2000. This is in direct response to the growing awareness that new teachers must be able to effectively integrate technological tools into their own classrooms. There is a growing need for the adaptability and context-aware education that digital resources can deliver. Higher education institutions need to rise to the technological challenge. Two of the UK's Joint Information Systems Committees (JISCs) are

investigating, testing, and learning more about a wide range of technologies for application in higher education.[15]

3.10 Assessment

In Higher Education Organizations, assessment plays a crucial role. How students are tested has a significant impact on how they learn and how far they may go in their studies. Despite the importance of evaluation and feedback, many organizations providing higher education organizations continue to struggle with these tasks because of rising costs, shrinking resources, and rising student expectations. Institutions should have procedures in place for dealing with violations of assessment requirements and appealing assessment judgments. JISC in the United Kingdom has been engaged in technology-enhanced assessment for more than a decade, JISC is promoting research on technical and interoperability issues related to online testing and broader technical, pedagogical, and institutional considerations related to the efficient use of a variety of technologies that support assessment and feedback. [16]

3.11 Combating Plagiarism

Plagiarism has been a source of growing concern in the higher education system. There were few prominent instances of plagiarism in the 1990s, but the global trend toward massification in higher education has prompted fears among academics that plagiarism has become widespread. Plagiarism prevention is a top priority in the academic world. We fear that the credibility of UK higher education degrees is jeopardized if nothing has been done to address rising concerns and probable cases of plagiarism and cooperation. Plagiarism is now seen seriously enough in the UK for scholars to seek advice on handling it. JISC JISCPAS to disseminate best practices and provide advice on avoiding plagiarism in all its forms.[17]

3.12 The Next Generation of Workers

Even the most well-run school would fail if its faculty lacked the necessary expertise; without skilled instructors, students would get a subpar education and researchers would be unable to advance their fields. For universities to effectively teach the curriculum, including employability skills, they must train their conventional teaching personnel in new capacities and adopt innovative ways to educate. Higher education institutions will have to train instructors and that particular instructor specifically to work with students who have varying and often difficult learning requirements. Higher education institutions may provide various training opportunities for their employees to help them stay current in the field and grow as needed. The next generation of workers must realize that learning is a lifelong pursuit. So they

must continuously evolve to keep up with the dynamic tertiary education landscape. NCATE in the United States is stepping up its performance-based, technology-focused standards for the year 2000 to directly address the requirement for new teachers to be proficient in the use of Technology, in their own teaching. The U.S. Department of Education's new initiative "Preparing Tomorrow's Educators to Use Technology" allocates \$75 million to meet this need. Addition of this, JISC provides tools to universities and their personnel to aid in the development of faculty and administrators in UK higher education.[18]

4. CLASSIFICATION PROBLEMS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Here, we categorize the problems currently facing higher education according to the literature published on the topic and its potential to shed light on the various causes and solutions to the problem. In table one, we show that problem (A) is related to the problem (B) and provide citations to back up our claim. We divide the difficulties into three categories, all of which have an impact on quality and productivity. The difficulties are broken down into different categories, as shown in Figure one.

Figure 1. Classification of Difficulties in Higher Education

We organize these obstacles such as if one group issue is solved, it will have a positive effect on the quality and efficiency of the problems it affects at the higher levels. Specifically, problems in group 3 have an effect on problems in group two, and problems in group 2 have

an impact on issues, If any of the problems in group three improves its quality or efficiency, the issues that are influenced or interrelated with or by this challenge will also improve automatically. Based on the data in the Table, we can see that evaluation has a significant impact on several different types of issues, including accreditation, the quality of teaching and learning, student retention, and plagiarism; as a result of it, we place assessment in the second group and all the challenges influenced by assessment in the first. [19]

We have thus placed evaluation in the third category, with accreditation, quality of instruction, student retention, and instances of plagiarism making up the second. To the same standard by which we categorize all other difficulties. Funding for Group 1 is affected by problems including student retention, research quality, accreditation, and broadening participation, which are all part of Group two. When we discover a bidirectional relationship between two difficulties, we place them in the same category. Since they are interrelated, we placed curricular alignment and student employability in the same cluster. Due to the importance of these issues, we placed financing and HE management and oversight in their own category, Group one. These are the two biggest obstacles we've run against, and fixing them is essential for addressing the others, so we didn't try to downgrade them.[21-22]

5. The Goi has Introduced Innovations

India's government has taken the necessary steps to lower the prohibitive cost of higher education by creating more state-run universities and other institutions of higher education.

5.1 Establishment of New Central Universities

As of January 15, 2009, 16 new Central Universities were formed in States (except for Goa) that did not previously have one; in Jammu and Kashmir, there are two Central Universities, one in the Kashmir Division and another in the Jammu Division. In addition to Jammu and Kashmir, the unrecognized states of Bihar, Jharkhand, Orissa, Gujarat, Haryana, Punjab, Rajasthan, Kerala, Karnataka, Himachal Pradesh, Goa, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Uttarakhand, and Tamil Nadu have each created a Central University. Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya in Chhattisgarh, Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya in Madhya Pradesh, and Hemwati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University in Uttarakhand are the three State Universities that have turned into Central Universities.

5.2 Indira Gandhi National Tribal University

An Act of Parliament created IGNTU, located in Amarkantak, Madhya Pradesh. It started its academic operations in the academic year 2008–2009. The university offers undergraduate and graduate programmes in a series of subject areas. The University is a teaching &

affiliating institution that facilitates and as well as supports opportunities for higher learning and research facilities for the nation's tribal population.

6. Construction of 374 Degree-Granting Institutions in Educationally Underdeveloped Areas

If a region has a Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) lower than the national average, the Ministry of Education will establish a Model Degree College there. A total of 374 districts fit this description, according to the findings of a recent study. The state government is expected to submit proposals for the creation of such universities. The Universities that are included in the Government's plan to increase higher education's availability, participation, and reach is this program.

7. A Plan to Incentivize State Governments to Foster the Growth of Post-secondary Educational Institutions

Currently, a plan is proposed to incentivize states to create new universities and expand current ones. Establishing new higher education institutions/expanding existing higher education institutions will be supported by the federal government at a ratio of 1:2 (1:1 for Special Category States) under this new Scheme. Universities, Colleges, and Engineering Institutions, as well as the establishment of new universities, are among the concrete goals of the XI Plan and XII Plan.

8. Helping Public Colleges and Universities in Hidden States

While State University affiliated colleges fall under UGC's purview, they are not eligible for funding because they lack the necessary infrastructure and faculty. For universities and colleges that serve underserved areas to qualify for UGC funding, the Ministry plans to provide them with additional resources. The XIst Plan is designed to increase the financing of institutions that have been approved to receive UGC Act Section 12B grants.

9. Strengthening Science-Based University Research and Higher Education

With the quantity and quality of scientific research in India declining, a committee chaired by Prof. M.M. Sharma was appointed to lead the charge in reviving university-based basic science. Efforts have begun to improve university-level scientific education or research in response to the Task Force's recommendations. The primary goal of the plan is to provide financial assistance to the university and college faculty members so that they may carry out research projects in their respective fields. The UGC has been working to advance education and investigation in cutting-edge fields such as the humanities, social sciences, languages,

poetry, pure sciences, engineering and or technology, medicine, medical agriculture science, etc. Permanent/Regular/retired faculty members of the universities and institutions that have been recognised under section 2(f) and certified suitable to receive funds under 12 B of the UGC Act 1956, are the only ones who are entitled to apply for grants under this act.

10. Policy Measures

Throughout the years, the government of India has implemented several policy measures that have helped to create an ideal ecology for higher education. [23]

10.1 National Knowledge Commission (NKC)

Since the 21st century has been dubbed the "knowledge century" on a global scale, every country is now engaged in fierce rivalry in the realms of education and innovation. with a heightened emphasis on quality, infrastructure, and information. As India's official think tank, it is tasked with formulating strategies to improve the country's higher education system and give the country a leg up in the knowledge- and service-intensive global economy. India's former prime minister, Dr. Manmohan Singh, signed this into law on June 13th, 2005. The purpose of the commission is to get advice on the policy that the prime minister has launched which is about education and research policy, as well as changes that would position India to become a major competitive force in the global knowledge economy. The panel was tasked with analyzing the need for changes in the areas of education, research facilities, and intellectual property law, and making recommendations to the Government of India. For the sake of a more open and efficient government that makes use of modern technology.

10.2 RUSA (Rashtriya Uchchatar Sikhsha Abhiyan)

India's education system has flourished. All thanks to progressive policies. The education sector has benefited dramatically from initiatives like the 2001-launched Sarva Sikhsha Abhiyan and the 2009-launched Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan, both of which aim to increase enrollment in and completion of secondary school. The UGC, as the governing authority for Indian universities, ensures that the country's higher education system is always evolving and improving. The University Grants Commission (UGC) is responsible for allocating funds for research and development inside universities, and its allocations are sufficient for colleges of centrally financed institutions in India under the policy under Section 12B and Section 2(f) of the UGC Act. There are 574 universities and 35,539 colleges in India in the year 31st of March 2012, according to statistics, with 214 of those universities being beyond the purview of Sections 12B & 2(f) of the UGC Act. The government in this country

runs a considerable number of institutions, Still, it spends relatively little on higher education overall, making it difficult to bring about needed changes and stifling opportunities for creativity and progress. Consequently, the NDC recommended, as a part of the 12th five-year plan, a distinct strategy for state/Union Territories to improve colleges and universities.

11. The Framework of a Network for Educational Innovation

Despite its potential to provide light on the sources of power behind the dissemination of knowledge, centralization in educational networks has been chiefly ignored (de Lima, 2010). A network's social hierarchy was inferred from examining its degree of centralization. Some professors in higher education may benefit much from the insights of their colleagues on the topic of educational innovations. Still, they may not reciprocate the same level of openness in their knowledge sharing.[24]

Most academic departments have clubs or organizations in which teachers participate. According to the literature, campus networks have become increasingly hierarchical due to the widespread adoption of corporate management principles in public institutions. In addition, a hierarchical structure in a social network might be brought about by differences in organizational functions. Instructors at universities may be recently appointed or hired as tenured professors, or even wholly independent professionals with no ties to the institution. Due to the varying responsibilities of each member of the organization, a hierarchical structure may develop. This structure is probably already present in campus networks. It may also characterize emerging networks between instructors in higher education, such as networks formed and supported by educational reform programs seeking to improve teaching quality via educational innovations. Consequently, we suggest that:

H1: At first glance, the structure of educational innovation networks seems to be hierarchical. The results of educational reforms obstruct when schools are centralized. Similarly, instructors in higher education who participated in an instructional development program said that the presence of hierarchy was a significant barrier to collaboration.

Pointed out that (network) interventions may have a beneficial effect on the structure of social networks. Conferences for educators, workshops for groups, seminars for professionals, and other similar activities are supported by either government funding or university efforts. With the higher education system, teachers can benefit from network interventions in several ways, including the chance to make connections with colleagues from different departments or institutional roles. During a curriculum improvement project, the positive impact of interventions can be seen empirically. However, rather than being a

discrete, one-time programme, these sorts of interventions are often continuous activities. Consequently, we will assume that:

H2: As a result of network interventions, the hierarchical structure of educational innovation networks spawned and supported by reform programs tends to flatten over time.

12. The Factors that Shape Networks for Educational Innovation

Researchers have shown that the structure of a person's social network isn't the only factor that matters when it comes to the spread of innovation. Since originality and invention occur within the organizational setting where a person plunges there is a strong correlation between these factors.

The organizational climate is a reflection of this setting since it represents the workers' consensus on how they work. Some academics describe "psychological climate" as an employee's own unique experience of the workplace, which allows "organizational climate" the personal characteristic of the workforce. Scholars have advised, "a facet-specific climate approach where climate has a focus and is related to something of interest" to provide meaningful findings and contribute to organizational theory, where "climate" may refer to various factors of the working environment. Using this method, you may determine which factors inside your company's culture are responsible for producing the results.[25]

The orientation towards innovation in teaching, or the creative teaching environment, is relevant as a feature of the organizational climate in the context of educational advances in higher education. This latter phrase represents the consensus among faculty in higher education about their working circumstances, which may encourage and discourage new approaches to instruction. Definition of Innovative Teaching Climate is one side to characterize innovative teaching climate as a personal trait of the professors in higher education who have the responsibility of interpreting it within their university departments. Researchers have shown that universities' penchant for innovation is a crucial factor in the spread of new methods of teaching and learning. As was said before, very little is known about how different teacher traits affect the organization of academic networks in higher education. Research in this field may provide light on the relationship between a conducive environment for pedagogical innovation and the development of networks for sharing best practices in education.[26]

13. Conclusion

As the government considers globalizing higher education for change and standards in the educational system, the current environment would be challenging for India's higher education system. The effectiveness with which Indian colleges and institutions address the sector's global concerns would be called into severe doubt by this. Few believe that expanding educational options worldwide is. It will result in high-quality instruction and research. Students are allowed to understand present and upcoming issues in depth. Even though we are generating graduates at a rapid pace these days, many of them are still unemployed. To adjust this mentality and transform it, we must take appropriate steps to boost employability. So it's time to adapt to change and modify to provide high-quality education. We know that higher education today is at a crossroads and must turn around to serve as a beacon of hope for students throughout the country.

About the Authors:

Name: C. P. SHivachandra

Designation: Research Scholar

University: Kannada Adhyayana Peetha Hampi, Karnataka.

Department: Kannada

My Research Topic : Oral Study of Mukri Community from Uttara Kannada District.

cpshivachandra@gmail.com

Name: Chaitra Pandurang Naik

Designation: Research Scholar

University: Karnatak University Dharwad

Department: English

Research Topic: Dalit Consciousness and Gender Disparity in Meena Kandasamy's Fiction: A Study.

Po: Karki Tq: Honnavar

Dist: Uttara Kannada

State: Karnataka

Pin Code: 581341

naikc155@gmail.com

14. References:

- McCord, A. (2003). Institutional repositories: Enhancing Teaching, Learning, and Research. *EDUCAUSE Evolving Technologies Committee*, 287-297.
- Al-Kurdi, O. F., El-Haddadeh, R., & Eldabi, T. (2020). The role of organizational climate in managing knowledge sharing among academics in higher education. *International Journal of Information Management*, 50, 217–227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.05.018>
- Al-Kurdi, O., El-Haddadeh, R., & Eldabi, T. (2018). Knowledge transfer in higher education institutions: A systematic review. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 31(2), 226–246. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEIM-09-2017-0129>
- Amabile, T. M. (1988). A model of creativity and innovation in organizations. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 10(1), 123–167.
- Ansell, C., Lundin, M., & Öberg, P. O. (2017). Learning networks among Swedish municipalities: Is Sweden a small world? In J. Glückler, E. Lazega, & I. Hammer (Eds.), *Knowledge and networks* (pp. 315–336). Springer.
- Ashkanasy, N. M., Wilder, C. P. M., & Peterson, M. F. (2000). *Handbook of organizational culture and climate*. Sage.
- Benz-Gydat, M., Jütte, W., Lobe, C., Walber, M. (2021). Neue Lehre an der Hochschule. Verstetigung innovativer Lehrprojekte in sozialen Hochschulwelten. [New teaching in higher education and Sustainability of innovative teaching projects in social university environments]. WBV. <https://doi.org/10.3278/6004902w>
- Bock, G. W., Zmud, R. W., Kim, Y. G., & Lee, J. N. (2005). Behavioral intention formation in knowledge sharing: Examining the roles of extrinsic motivators, social-psychological forces, and organizational climate. *MIS Quarterly*, 29(1), 87–111.
- Bruckmann, S., & Carvalho, T. (2018). Understanding change in higher education: An archetypal approach. *Higher Education*, 76(4), 629–647. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-018-0229-2>
- Chester, G. (2001). Plagiarism Detection and Prevention: final report of the JISC electronic plagiarism detection project. Available at www.jisc.ac.uk. 4th July 2022.
- Christakis, N. A., & Fowler, J. H. (2013). Social contagion theory: Examining dynamic social networks and human behavior. *Statistics in Medicine*, 32(4), 556–577. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.5408>
- Civis, M., Diaz-Gibson, J., López, S., & Moolenaar, N. (2019). Collaborative and innovative climates in pre-service educator programs: The role of social capital. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 98, 224–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.08.019>
- Clark, T. N. (1968). Institutionalization of innovations in higher education: Four models. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 13(1), 1–25.
- Cohen, D. K., & Ball, D. L. (2007). Educational innovation and the problem of scale. In B. Schneider & S. K. McDonald (Eds.), *Scale-up in education: Ideas in principle* (pp. 19–36). Rowman & Littlefield Publications.

- Daly, A. J., & Finnigan, K. S. (2010). A bridge between worlds: Understanding network structure to understand change strategy. *Journal of Educational Change*, 11(2), 111–138. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-009-9102-5>
- Damanpour, F. (1991). Organizational innovation: A meta-analysis of effects of determinants and moderators. *Academy of Management Journal*, 34(3), 555–590. <https://doi.org/10.5465/256406>
- De Lima, J. Á. (2010). Thinking more deeply about networks in education. *Journal of Educational Change*, 11(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-008-9099-1>
- Erdős, P., & Rényi, A. (1959). On random graphs. *Publicationes Mathematicae*, 6, 290–297. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400841356.38>
- Feixas, M., Martínez-Usarralde, M. J., & López-Martín, R. (2018). Do teaching innovation projects make a difference? Assessing the impact of small-scale funding. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 24(4), 267–283. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13583883.2017.1417470>
- Fredrickson, M. M., & Chen, Y. (2019). Permutation and randomization tests for network analysis. *Social Networks*, 59, 171–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socnet.2019.08.001>
- Glenda Crosling, Margaret Heagney Liz Thomas (2009). “Improving student retention in higher education,” *Australian Universities Review*, 51(2), http://educationalpolicy.org/pdf/AUR_epitoday_090917.pdf
- JS Eaton (2009). “An overview of US accreditation,” Council for Higher Education Accreditation. Retrieved from http://chea.org/pdf/2009.06_Overview_of_US_Accreditation.pdf.
- Liz Thomas (2002). Student retention in higher education: the role of institutional habitus. *Journal of Educational Policy*, 17(4), 423-442, <http://www.ulster.ac.uk/star/resources/stu%20retention.pdf>
- Mille, T. (2009). Formative computer-based assessment in higher education: the effectiveness of feedback in supporting student learning. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 34(2), 181–192.
- Tiropanis, T., Davis, H., Millard, D., Weal, M., & White, S. (2009). Linked Data as a Foundation for the Deployment of Semantic Applications in Higher Education. I *ISWEL'09: Ontologies and Social Semantic Web for Intelligent Educational Systems, AIED'09 Conference*, Brighton, UK.